

S25 - CSE08

2025 INESC TEC

SUMMER INTERNSHIPS

FINAL SESSION PRESENTATIONS

INTRODUCTIONS

Personal Information

Henrique Teixeira
José Paradela

Some Background

2º, Inteligência Artificial e Ciência de Dados
4º, Engenharia Eletrotécnica e de Computadores

Why a summer internship

To learn new things about research and the area we chose as well as to gain new experience

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CONTEXT

Aceleração de IA num SoC RISC-V Sintetizável a partir de Alto Nível

CTM

Nuno Paulino

OBJECTIVES

- Extend RISC-V core with hardware for energy efficient calculations for ML inference
- Evaluate cost benefit trade off with a baseline system
- Contribute to an ongoing EU project on edge computing (<https://www.aiqready.eu/>)

DEVELOPED WORK

- **Studied** existing **RISC-V Core** implemented in C++ → RISC++
- **Studied theory** on **Logarithmic Number System (LNS)** and **implementations** of LNS Units in CPU cores
- **Developed linear approximation** of addition and subtraction LNS functions and **calculated the error** for each **table size in LNS16**
 - Compared LNS16's vs. FP32's and FP16's
- **Designed hardware** for addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and square root in LNS
- **Tested** the LNS Unit in the RISC++ Core **on a FPGA**

EDGE A-IQ READY

THEORY

LNS Format

$$x = (-1)^{S_x} 2^{L_x}$$

S_x	L_x Integer Part	L_x Fractional Part
1 bit	8 bits	7 bits

$$S_x = \begin{cases} 1, & x < 0 \\ 0, & x \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

$$L_x = \log_2(|x|)$$

LNS Addition

$$L_x + \log_2(1 + 2^{L_y - L_x})$$

LNS Multiplication

$$L_x + L_y$$

LNS Square Root

$$L_x \gg 1$$

LNS Subtraction

$$L_x + \log_2(1 - 2^{L_y - L_x})$$

LNS Division

$$L_x - L_y$$

$$|x| > |y| \Leftrightarrow L_x > L_y$$

$$\log_2(1 \pm 2^{L_y - L_x}) \text{ ?}$$

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LNS

LUTs: 4674

FFs: 2288

DSPs: 5

Without LNS

LUTs: 2418

FFs: 1659

DSPs: 3

RESULTS

- Implemented the LNSU in about **500 lines of code**
- **Tables used** for linear approximation with **only 192 bytes combined**
- Maximum **throughput** with frequency up to **125MHz on the FPGA**
- **Simpler RTL circuit** than **FP32/FP16**
- **Faster theoretical** (Core didn't have a FPU) **operations** than **FP32/16**

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ACQUIRED SKILLS & NEW KNOWLEDGE

- RISC-V
- Hardware design
- High Level Synthesis
- Edge Computing
- Design Space Exploration

Conclusions and Next Steps

- **Implemented** an **effective** approach to **calculate and optimize LNS** operations in 3 weeks
- **Developed** the **ground** for future work in **future Master Theses**
- **Next: Study** new **LNS formats** and explore **new ways** to improve **addition** and **subtraction** approaches

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